

On the Study of Polyhalides. Part II. Formation and Dissociation of Chloro-dibromides and Tri-bromides of Sodium, Potassium, Strontium and Barium.

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Polyhalides of the alkali metals have been the subject of numerous investigations and polyhalides of rubidium, caesium and ammonium, stable at ordinary temperatures have long been known. Some references to the literature of the polyhalides of the alkali metals were given in the first part of this work (Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 259). So far the formation of alkali polyhalides have been studied with the aid of the solubility, partition, conductivity and spectroscopic experiments. In the present paper, the formation and dissociation of the polyhalogen compounds of the metals of the alkali and alkaline earths have been studied with the aid of the freezing point method (*cf.* Ray, *loc. cit.*). It has been shown that the formation of the polyhalogen compounds like NaClBr_2 , KClBr_2 , Sr_2ClBr_2 , Ba_2ClBr_2 , NaBr_3 , KBr_3 , Sr_2Br_3 and Ba_2Br_3 can be definitely established by this method. The reactions were always studied in dilute solutions ($N/2$ to $N/16$) and with moderate concentrations of halogens. The action of iodine on the chlorides could not be studied owing to the sparing solubility of iodine in the dilute solutions of the chlorides.

The equilibrium constants of the reactions

and

(where X stands for Na, K, $\frac{1}{2}\text{Sr}$ or $\frac{1}{2}\text{Ba}$) or expressed ionically

and the heats of formation of the complexes ClBr_2 and Br_3 have been calculated on the basis of the above equations.

The interaction between the halogens and the halides of strontium and barium cannot be represented, owing to the ionisation of these halides by stages, in the above simple way. The reaction for instance, between bromine and barium chloride can be expressed in the following way:

In very dilute solutions the normal reaction (i) takes place. In concentrated solutions of BaCl_2 , the conversion of BaCl_2 into Ba^{++} and Cl^- ions may not be complete and the reaction may take place to a certain extent according to the scheme (ii). Besides, the reaction may also be molecular (iii). It will be noticed that in the case of strontium and barium, the equilibrium constants are found to vary to a certain extent. The reason being that the degree of dissociation of the halides of the metals of the alkaline earths being small in comparison with that of the alkali metals, the change in their degree of dissociation by the formation of the complexes cannot be neglected. Besides the likely formation of BaCl_2Br_2 and the higher complexes (the solution becoming sufficiently concentrated at the low temperature) would lead to some complications. Moreover, there is also some likelihood of hydrolysis taking place.

In the following experiments the calculation of the equilibrium constants, the degree of dissociation of the halides, the heats of formation of the complexes, etc., were calculated as in the first part of this work (*loc. cit.*).

The method of procedure is practically identical with that described in the first part of this paper for polyhalides of hydrogen (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I.

Formation of NaClBr₂.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant <i>K</i> .	Dissocia- tion con- stant 1/ <i>K</i> .	Degree of dissociation <i>a</i> ₂ .
<i>N</i> /2-NaCl	1.795	0.929	0.0
<i>N</i> /2-NaCl + Br ₂	0.070	0.2179	0.4691	5.478	0.1825	0.3212
„	0.050	0.1564	0.3367	5.217	0.1918	0.3198
„	0.042	0.1376	0.2962	5.505	0.1817	0.3052
<i>N</i> /4-NaCl	0.910	0.4645	0.0
<i>N</i> /4-NaCl + Br ₂	0.120	0.2401	0.5169	5.738	0.1743	0.4998
„	0.107	0.2179	0.4690	5.773	0.1732	0.4910
„	0.080	0.1623	0.3494	5.293	0.1889	0.4927
<i>N</i> /8-NaCl	0.460	0.2322	0.0
<i>N</i> /8-NaCl + Br ₂	0.157	0.2351	0.5059	5.913	0.1691	0.6677
„	0.125	0.1905	0.4102	5.853	0.1709	0.6561
„	0.065	0.1042	0.2245	5.843	0.1712	0.6237
<i>N</i> /16-NaCl	0.230	0.1160	0.0
<i>N</i> /16-NaCl + Br ₂	0.150	0.1880	0.4048	6.095	0.1641	0.7979
„	0.105	0.1324	0.2852	5.542	0.1804	0.7930
„	0.067	0.0871	0.1877	5.802	0.1724	0.7686

Mean value of $K = 5.654$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.1769$. Mean temp. = -0.94° .

TABLE II.

Formation of KClBr₂.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissocia- tion con- stant 1/K.	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2 .
N/2-KCl	1·805	0·929	0·0
N/2-KCl + Br ₂	0·075	0·2444	0·5261	5·891	0·1697	0·3069
„	0·062	0·2033	0·4378	5·781	0·1730	0·3049
„	0·040	0·1324	0·2852	5·895	0·1651	0·3020
N/4-KCl	0·915	0·4645	0·0
N/4-KCl + Br ₂	0·107	0·2222	0·4785	5·973	0·167	0·4816
„	0·080	0·1795	0·3864	5·945	0·168	0·4458
„	0·070	0·1479	0·3183	5·549	0·180	0·4735
N/8-KCl	0·465	0·2322	0·0
N/8-KCl + Br ₂	0·137	0·2068	0·4452	5·741	0·174	0·6624
„	0·105	0·1590	0·3422	5·657	0·177	0·6606
„	0·080	0·1247	0·2686	5·577	0·179	0·6412
N/16-KCl	0·230	0·116	0·0
N/16-KCl + Br ₂	0·115	0·1636	0·3522	5·926	0·1691	0·7030
„	0·105	0·1316	0·2833	5·619	0·1781	0·7979
„	0·080	0·1017	0·2190	5·315	0·1882	0·7866

Mean value of $K=5·739$. Mean value of $1/K=0·174$. Mean temp. = $-0·98^\circ$.

The value of the dissociation constant as obtained by Job (*Ann. Chim.*, 1928, *x*, 9, 148), at 16° is 0·190. The heat of formation of ClBr₂ ion was calculated between the temperatures, $-0·98^\circ$ and 16° (Job) and was found to be 798 calories; the value obtained by other investigators are as follows: Job (*loc. cit.*) from KClBr₂, 1000 calories and Ray (*loc. cit.*) from HClBr₂, 1044 calories.

TABLE III.
Formation of Sr_{1/2}ClBr₂.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissocia- tion con- stant 1/K.	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2 .
N/4-SrCl ₂	0.675	0.4645	0.0
N/4-SrCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.125	0.2188	0.4710	12.02	0.0832	0.5714
..	0.065	0.1274	0.2742	12.11	0.0826	0.5104
..	0.055	0.1026	0.2208	10.00	0.100	0.5363
N/8-SrCl ₂	0.375	0.2322	0.0
N/8-SrCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.125	0.1846	0.3974	10.88	0.0917	0.6772
..	0.095	0.1453	0.3127	10.70	0.0934	0.6539
N/16-SrCl ₂	0.230	0.116	0.0
N/16-SrCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.090	0.1265	0.2723	10.10	0.0992	0.7115
..	0.057	0.0863	0.1858	10.48	0.0955	0.6604

Mean value of $K = 10.90$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0918$. Mean temp. = -0.51° .

TABLE IV.
Formation of Ba_{1/2}ClBr₂.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissocia- tion con- stant 1/K.	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2 .
N/4-BaCl ₂	0.645	0.4645	0.0
N/4-BaCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.135	0.2240	0.4820	13.53	0.0739	0.6029
..	0.100	0.1675	0.3606	11.35	0.0881	0.5970
..	0.040	0.0786	0.1692	12.70	0.0787	0.5088
N/8-BaCl ₂	0.330	0.2322	0.0
N/8-BaCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.115	0.1590	0.3422	13.34	0.0750	0.7235
..	0.060	0.0888	0.1914	13.06	0.0767	0.6751
N/16-BaCl ₂	0.215	0.1160	0.0
N/16-BaCl ₂ + Br ₂	0.100	0.1402	0.3017	12.74	0.0785	0.7136
..	0.060	0.0914	0.1969	14.49	0.0690	0.6561

Mean value of $K = 13.03$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0767$. Mean temp. = -0.48° .

TABLE V.

Formation of NaBr₃.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissocia- tion con- stant 1/K.	Degree of dissocia- tion α_2 .
N/4-NaBr	0.925	0.4645	0.0
N/4-NaBr + Br ₂	0.067	0.2679	0.5766	22.63	0.0442	0.2450
..	0.057	0.2478	0.5935	23.15	0.0432	0.2896
..	0.037	0.1768	0.3807	21.98	0.0455	0.2091
N/8-NaBr	0.465	0.2322	0.0
N/8-NaBr + Br ₂	0.110	0.2418	0.5206	22.28	0.0449	0.4548
..	0.077	0.1888	0.4065	22.55	0.0443	0.4078
..	0.032	0.0972	0.2093	22.86	0.0438	0.3284
N/16-NaBr	0.235	0.1160	0.0
N/16-NaBr + Br ₂	0.122	0.1897	0.4084	21.60	0.0464	0.6431
..	0.080	0.1368	0.2944	23.50	0.0425	0.5851
..	0.045	0.0881	0.1895	23.41	0.0421	0.5112

Mean value of $K = 22.66$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0441$. Mean temp. = -0.65° .

The values of the dissociation constants obtained by Griffith, McKeown and Winn (*loc. cit.*) are as follows: $1/K$ at 16.5° , 0.0560 and $1/K$ at 21.5° , 0.0593.

The heat of formation of Br₃ ion was calculated between the temperatures -0.65° and 21.5° (Griffith, McKeown and Winn, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 101) and was found to be 1917 calories. This is of the same order as those found by other investigators as given below:

Berthelot (<i>Compt. rend.</i> , 1882, 94, 1618)	1290 calories.
Lewis and Randall (<i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1916, 38, 1618) from KBr ₃	1650 ..
Job (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	from KBr ₃ ... 2030 ..
Ray (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	from HBr ₃ ... 1467 ..

TABLE VI.
Formation of KBr_3 .

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K .	Dissociation constant $1/K$.	Degree of dissociation α_2 .
$N/4\text{-KBr}$	0.920	0.4645	0.0
$N/4\text{-KBr} + \text{Br}_2$	0.052	0.2308	0.4967	23.17	0.0432	0.2253
„	0.040	0.1897	0.4084	22.06	0.0453	0.2061
„	0.027	0.1401	0.3017	22.81	0.0438	0.1927
$N/8\text{-KBr}$	0.470	0.2322	0.0
$N/8\text{-KBr} + \text{Br}_2$	0.107	0.2401	0.5169	23.44	0.0427	0.4457
„	0.080	0.1940	0.4177	22.52	0.0444	0.4124
„	0.047	0.1294	0.2723	22.63	0.0440	0.4349
$N/16\text{-KBr}$	0.230	0.116	0.0
$N/16\text{-KBr} + \text{Br}_2$	0.135	0.2077	0.4471	23.27	0.0430	0.6500
„	0.097	0.1598	0.3441	22.77	0.0439	0.6019
„	0.057	0.1052	0.2263	23.16	0.0422	0.5422

Mean value of $K = 22.87$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0437$. Mean temp. = -0.65° .

The values of the dissociation constants, obtained by other investigators are given below:

Jones and Hartmann (<i>J. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.</i> , 1916, 20, 295)	...	0.051 at 0°
Jakowkin, (calculated by Lewis and Randall, <i>loc. cit.</i>)	...	0.062 at 25°
Worley (calculated by Linhart, <i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1918, 40, 158)	0.063	at 26.5°
Worley (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1905, 87, 1107)	...	0.065 at 32.5°
Griffith, McKeown and Winn (<i>loc. cit.</i>)		{ 0.056 at 16.5° 0.0576 at 21.5°

The heat of formation was calculated between the temperatures -0.65° and 21.5° (Griffith and others) and was found to be 1976 calories, which agrees very closely with the values obtained by other investigators (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE VII.

Formation of Sr_{1/2}Br₃.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissociation constant 1/K.	Degree of dissociation α_2 .
N/4-SrBr ₂	0.690	0.4645	0.0
N/4-SrBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.095	0.2564	0.5520	70.32	0.0142	0.3705
..	0.065	0.2197	0.4729	62.99	0.0159	0.2959
..	0.035	0.1512	0.3256	56.78	0.0176	0.2315
N/8-SrBr ₂	0.390	0.2322	0.0
N/8-SrBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.075	0.1897	0.4084	66.88	0.0150	0.3954
..	0.035	0.1198	0.2579	63.16	0.0191	0.2922
N/16-SrBr ₂	0.235	0.116	0.0
N/16-SrBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.085	0.1665	0.3588	52.32	0.0191	0.5102
..	0.060	0.1350	0.2907	56.98	0.0176	0.4445

Mean value of $K = 61.34$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0168$. Mean temp. = -0.48° .

TABLE VIII.

Formation of Ba_{1/2}Br₃.

	Depression actual.	Depression calc.	Conc. of Br in g. per 25 c.c.	Equilibrium constant K.	Dissociation constant 1/K.	Degree of dissociation α_2 .
N/4-BaBr ₂	0.680	0.4645	0.0
N/4-BaBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.115	0.2914	0.6273	73.60	0.0135	0.3947
..	0.055	0.2033	0.4378	75.08	0.0133	0.2705
..	0.035	0.1538	0.3311	65.48	0.0150	0.2329
N/8-BaBr ₂	0.380	0.2322	0.0
N/8-BaBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.100	0.2051	0.4416	74.08	0.0135	0.4875
..	0.065	0.1718	0.3698	75.12	0.0133	0.3784
N/16-BaBr ₂	0.230	0.116	0.0
N/16-BaBr ₂ + Br ₂	0.095	0.1872	0.4024	61.01	0.0164	0.5076
..	0.055	0.1290	0.2777	62.90	0.0159	0.4263

Mean value of $K = 69.48$. Mean value of $1/K = 0.0144$. Mean temp. = -0.51° .

From a comparison of the equilibrium constants of the reactions involving the formation of ClBr_2 , ClI_2 , Br_3 , BrI_2 , and I_3 ions it will be seen that the equilibrium constant for the same complex ion varied with the nature of the cation of the halide employed. This is evident from the values tabulated below:

Value of Equilibrium Constants.

	Cations.		
	H_2	Na .	K .
ClBr_2	1.726 ¹	5.654	5.739
	(-1.5°)	(-1°)	(-1°)
	1.412 ²		5.263 ³
	(30°)		(16°)
ClI_2	1.836 ¹		3.571 ³
	(-3.8°)		(16°)
	1.60 ²	1.961 ⁴	2.325 ⁴
	(25°)	(25°)	(25°)
Br_3	20.515 ¹	22.66	22.87
	(-1°)	(-0.6°)	(-0.6°)
		16.86 ⁶	17.36 ⁶
		(21.5°)	(21.5°)
	16.2 ⁵		16.13 ⁵
	(25°)		(25°)
BrI_2			18.52 ³
			(16°)
	14.28 ²		12.99 ⁴
	(30°)		(25°)
I_3	772.7 ⁴	720.9 ⁴	719.4 ⁴
	(25°)	(25°)	(25°)

These divergences in the values of the equilibrium constants become strikingly evident from the following curves, obtained by

¹ Ray (*loc. cit.*).

² Rây and Sarkar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 21, 1449).

³ Job (*loc. cit.*).

⁴ Jakowkin (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1896, 20, 19).

⁵ Lewis and Randall (*loc. cit.*).

⁶ Griffith, McKeown and Winn (*loc. cit.*).

plotting the values of the equilibrium constants against the respective ionic radii. The values of the ionic radii for Na^+ (0.98\AA) and

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

K^+ (1.33\AA) were taken from Goldschmidt (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 26, 282). The ionic radius of H^+ being assumed to be less than that for Li^+ (0.78\AA) and was taken to be 0.5\AA . Slight temperature differences were neglected. The values of Br_3 (at 25°) and

BrI_2 (at 30°), in presence of sodium ion and potassium ion respectively, were calculated from data quoted above.

As it is intended only to indicate the influence of cationic volume upon the stability of any complex polyhalide ion formed, the nature of the curve or the relative values of the equilibrium constants are not in any way affected by tracing the curves for different temperatures for different complex ions.

It was assumed that the above reactions are all ionic, the constancy of the value of the equilibrium constants being obtained on that assumption. Thus for the formation of the complex ions, for instance ClBr_2 , the value of the equilibrium constant on this assumption should remain unchanged, irrespective of the nature of the cation, but actually they are found to differ. It will further be noticed, that in the case of the chloro-dibromo ions, this difference is the greatest; it then decreases and practically vanishes in the case of Br_3 ion, the differences again becoming pronounced in the case of BrI_2 and I_3 ions but in the opposite direction. This peculiar phenomenon cannot be explained by the assumption that the reaction is also to a certain extent molecular, the halide being completely dissociated in the dilute solutions employed.

The influence of this cationic volume upon the stability of the complex polyhalogen ion can be explained when not only the volume of the cation, but also the polarisability of the halogen molecule as well as that of the halogen ion is taken into consideration. As is well known, the polarisability of the halogen molecules and the halogen ions increases with their atomic volume, *i.e.*, in the order chlorine \rightarrow bromine \rightarrow iodine. On the other hand, the polarising capacity of the cations diminishes with their volume *i.e.*, in the order $\text{H} \rightarrow \text{Na} \rightarrow \text{K}$ etc.

The two extreme cases of HClBr_2 and HI_3 can now be represented by the following models:

Ionic_Radius.

In I the replacement of H⁺ by Na⁺ or K⁺ of larger volume will naturally increase the stability of ClBr₂ ions, whereas in II such replacement will diminish the stability of I'₃ to a certain extent as the polarising power of cation diminishes. This also accounts for the higher values of equilibrium constants with larger halogen molecules and ions, which are more easily polarisable. In I the Cl⁻ ion is not appreciably polarised on account of its smaller volume and greater electron-affinity.

The cases of strontium and barium were not considered, for in their cases the influence of the SrCl or BaCl ion besides Sr or Ba ion complicates the matter. Moreover, the values of the equilibrium constants obtained in their cases are not accurate but only approximate.

SUMMARY.

By means of the freezing point depressions, the formation of polyhalides of the metals of the alkali and the alkaline earths have been confirmed and their dissociation constants determined at their freezing points. From the dissociation constants at the freezing points and from those at other temperatures determined by different investigators, their heats of formation have also been calculated. The following table gives the values of the dissociation constants and the heat of formation of the complexes:

	NaClBr ₂	KClBr ₂	Sr _{1/2} ClBr ₂	Ba _{1/2} ClBr ₂	NaBr ₃	KBr ₃	Sr _{1/2} Br ₃	Ba _{1/2} Br ₃
Dissociation constant	0.1769	0.174	0.092	0.077	0.0441	0.0437	0.016	0.014
Heat of formation (calories)	...	798	1917	1976

The divergence in the values of the equilibrium constants for any complex polyhalide ion with different cations is attributed to the electrostatic forces operating between the cation, the halogen ion and the halogen molecule.

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